

A Study on the Application of Blue Ocean Strategy on Select National and International Entertainment Media

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Abstract

Blue Ocean is a wide, calm, deep unexplored space which represents an unknown / new market space which has little or no competition. Demand is created and not fought over in this market. On the other hand, Red ocean reflects Rivalry, cut throat competition and limited prospects for profit and growth. Due to competition the oceans turn bloody and thus the name Red ocean. In Blue Ocean Strategy the business houses change the market completely rather than competing in it. Blue ocean strategy is about identifying the right mix of benefits for the product or service of the entrepreneur which can address the pain and create gain for the Customers, if done well this can lead to making the competition irrelevant for the respective venture.

The paper aims to study two different markets and medias in the entertainment industry namely- 'Saregama Carvaan' and Netflix. A first look at Saregama's Carvaan and one would be filled with doubt as to why a veteran music company would launch a product that is easily half a decade behind in technology. Intuitively, this would have been an absolute reject in the age of video and music streaming services. However, a big box with 5000 preloaded songs, sold like hot cakes in 2018 in India and the primary reason for this was the strategy of finding a blue ocean for launch of their product. As on March 2019 the annual revenue earned by the company was 51.7 million dollars. Netflix, an American entertainment company is one of the largest such company operating worldwide. It started off with the business idea of DVD sales and providing movie services for rent. It slowly changed its business plan from rental per movie to monthly fees to using online platform for streaming videos and movies, with time to cater to the changing needs of the customers. Netflix has continuously adopted the Blue Ocean Strategy to differentiate itself from its competitors like Blockbuster and become successful. As of April 2019, it had total 154 million subscriptions (including free trials) out of which 148 million are paid subscriptions.

This study intends to fulfil the following objectives:

- To conduct an in-depth study on Blue Ocean Strategy to understand its meaning, importance, implementation and impact on the industry.
- To evaluate the application of Blue Ocean Strategy by Saregama in the Indian audio entertainment market and how it has impacted its performance and growth.
- To evaluate the application of Blue Ocean Strategy by Netflix in the international audio- visual entertainment market and how it has impacted its performance and growth.
- To do a SWOT analysis of the two companies for both before and after the adoption of Blue Ocean Strategy by them.

Keywords: Blue Ocean Strategy, Netflix BOS, Saregama BOS, SWOT analysis

1. Introduction

Blue Ocean Strategy was introduced to the World by eminent scholars W. Chan Kim and Renee Mauborgne. According to Blue Ocean strategy the best way to grow is to look for a new market space that is not crowded rather than to try for a larger share in the existing market, as existing markets get crowded leading to products becoming similar to each other and thereby leading to high competition and reducing the chances of higher profit, the trick instead should be focussed on new customers segments by providing customers a leap in their value. Leap in value for customers is not only restricted to just adding new technology instead it is about identifying the right mix of benefits for the product or service of the entrepreneur which can address the pain and create gain for the Customers, if done well this can lead to making the competition irrelevant for the respective venture.

Entertainment media refers to a mass communication medium via which an event, performance, or activity is designed and communicated to the mass.

The paper aims to study two different markets and Medias in the entertainment industry namely- Saregama Carvaan and Netflix, the former being chosen from National Market addressing the Audio media requirement and the latter being part of an international market addressing the audio –visual media. In this context it has become imperative to know how both these companies though part of a very crowded Entertainment Industry have identified a blue ocean for themselves and led their respective markets as leaders.

2. Literature Review

- Mi (2005) concluded that Blue Ocean Strategy helps the companies to break through the existing competition and create their own market space by providing them with both theoretical framework and practical guidelines for doing so. It requires the combination of value, profit and people propositions to achieve both differentiation and low cost to ultimately create value for the customers.
- Kim et al., (2006) in a case study on CJ- Global Logistics Service showed how it successfully implemented the Blue Ocean Strategy in the newly introduced third party logistics service providing industry. It achieved an advantage over its competitors by using innovative information technology (RFID- Radio Frequency Identification). By using a four-section framework the paper highlights how it successfully used electronic logistics service to emerge a leader in the market.
- Hollensen (2013) conducted a case study on Nintendo to understand the Blue Ocean Strategy implemented by it to differentiate itself from competitors like Microsoft and Sony. It was found that a Blue Ocean can turn red within 1-2 years of its creation due to various competitors trying to enter it to gain its related advantages. Thus, there should be a continuous reformulation of the strategy with time to keep the ocean blue and make the competition irrelevant.
- Kim and Mauborgne (2005) concluded that there is a particular pattern that unites the strategic moves for implementing the Blue Ocean Strategy and differentiates from all the strategies to compete in the red ocean. In a study on over 150 blue ocean examples in over 30 different industries spanning over more than 100 years from 1880 to 2000 found out how firms take steps to move out of the red ocean of competition to create a new uncontested market place to become a leader there.
- Chang (2010) in a case study on Bandit Cell-phones – an unbranded cell phone, analysed the Blue Ocean Strategy used by the said company to create a new market for itself. It introduced a new business model- combining low cost and added features helped it to create a large market potential in the developing countries including China.
- Lindic et al., (2012) suggested that the policies for the growth of a company should be from the entrepreneurial perspective. Empirical data on two successful business houses namely- Amazon.com and Slovenian gazelles was collected to study their Blue Ocean Strategies. The study reveals that there is a gap between the macro level of policy framing for the overall growth and the micro level for achieving immediate profits. The two should be aligned.

The present study distinguishes itself from the previous studies in a number of ways. It tries to do a SWOT analysis of the selected companies both before and after the implementation of a Blue Ocean Strategy to understand what impact the strategy had on their strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. The study intends to fulfil the research gap regarding the study of Blue Ocean Strategy by a national and an international company involved in entertainment industry.

3. Research Objectives

This study intends to fulfil the following objectives:

- To conduct an in-depth study on Blue Ocean Strategy to understand its meaning, importance and implementation.
- To evaluate the application of Blue Ocean Strategy by Saregama in the Indian audio entertainment market and how it has impacted its performance and growth.
- To evaluate the application of Blue Ocean Strategy by Netflix in the international audio- visual entertainment market and how it has impacted its performance and growth.
- To do a SWOT analysis of the two companies for both before and after the adoption of Blue Ocean Strategy by them.

4. Methodology

The study is done in the form of a case study on Saregama Cravan and Netflix. The data used in the study is secondary in nature collected from the internet and various journals. The strategy canvas of the selected companies has been presented through line graphs.

5. Theoretical Framework of Blue Ocean Strategy

Red ocean reflects Rivalry, cut throat completion and limited prospects for profit and growth due to completion the oceans turn bloody and thus the name Red ocean. On the other hand, Blue ocean reflects unexplored / new market space which has little or no competition and where demand is created and not fought over. Blue ocean strategy thus provides a leap in value to the customers along with simultaneous pursuit of cost efficiency.

Fig. 1. Source: Adopted from the book The Blue Ocean Strategies by W. Chan Kim and Renee Mauborgne

As shown in the figure above the creators of blue oceans, surprisingly, didn't use the competition as their benchmark. Instead, they followed a different strategic logic that is known as value innovation. Value innovation focuses on creating both value and innovation. Value without innovation tends to focus on value creation which is only restricted to adding new technology instead it is about identifying the right mix of benefits for the product or service of the entrepreneur which can address the pain and create gain for the Customers. The strategy is implemented through a four-action framework of: Raise, Create, Eliminate and Reduce.

Fig. 1.1. Source: Adopted from the book The Blue Ocean Strategies by W. Chan Kim and Renee Mauborgne

6. Analysis

6.1. Strategy Analysis of Saregama Carvaan

Saregama is one of the largest record labels in India owned by RP Sanjeev Goenka of RPG Group. Saregama music consists of a variety of Film music, Carnatic, Hindustani classical, Devotional etc. in all prominent Indian languages. It acquired four reputed South Indian music labels— *Sangeetha*, *Sargam*, Pyramid and Sea Records and established its strong foot hold in the media and entertainment industry. (Wikipedia)

Online music apps like Gaana, Saavn etc.; increasing piracy with intense competition in the Entertainment industry slowly took over the supremacy of the leader and with time the company started suffering continuous losses

Let’s have a quick look at the Swot analysis of the company to understand the need for pivoting leading to the new product Saregama Carvaan.

Strengths	Weakness
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.Saregama is one of the oldest and the largest record label in India 2. Saregama has an inventory of more than 70000 songs and 600 cassettes and CDs 3. Custodian of nearly half of all music ever recorded in India 4. Saregama provides the largest music repertoire across all genres and languages 5. Bands and Artists under Saregama umbrella 6. Purchased tracks remain in the cloud 7. Saregama now offers its consumer the opportunity to purchase albums online 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.Fierce competitions limits the scope for market expansion 2. Involves too much capital expenditure 3. inability to map the correct customer Segment 4. Inability to tap the younger generation hooked online for free and easy download of songs. 5. Purchasing cassettes and Cd’s slowly becoming obsolete
Opportunities	Threats
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.Rise in revenue by means of electronic downloads and ringtones in music industry 2. Indian television industry consists of 41% share in Indian advertising sector 3. Massive international presence of Indian film industry 4. The rapid growth of Indian Radio and Animation industry. 5. Provide old tracks/single track from new albums under a CC license 6. Subscription based streaming services 7. Create platform to distribute merchandise 8. Getting the consumers to collaborate will help in increasing the network of music 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Inflated distribution costs 2. Reduction in volumes due to piracy 3. Intense rivalry amongst competitors 4. Publication industry is overcrowded 5. High Entertainment tax adversely impacts the revenue 6. High cost of acquisition of rights 7. Lacklustre performance of the film industry 8. Competition from Unorganised or unbranded music stores.

Table 1. Swot analysis of the company

Cassette/s and CDs are becoming obsolete and on the other hand the older generation still tries to avoid complicated apps This led the Company to pivot its Strategy. It started to work on its weakness and utilised their strength and external opportunities to bridge the gap between the older crowd and Saregama’s existing vast library.

So instead of fighting in the crowded red ocean with so many competitors they devised for themselves a completely new market by launching Saregama Carvaan which is a retro style designed big box preloaded with 5000+ songs categorised into 80+ dedicated stations, coupled with features like Bluetooth and USB support, android compatibility etc within a reasonable price range.

People around the age group of 40+ who might not be that tech savvy to download the song of their choice from the free apps available like Gaana or Saavn. But the price range of over Rs. 6000 for a tool that would just play songs was again quite high for middleclass retired or near retirement age group of Indian population.

So, in the above situation despite having a quality product the situation analysis does not give us an accurate picture of success.

Let’s observe from the following table how the company via proper strategy turned the factors that could have gone against it into factors that became the USP for the immense success of the product. Thereby creating for itself Value Innovation and an unexplored uninhabited market space.

Gaana and Saavn were the closest competitors of Saregama, all being part of the crowded Music industry (Red Ocean). When both its competitors were into hardcore rivalry by providing free and easy download of latest hit

songs across all genres, Saregama took a different route it focussed on the Four Action Framework of Blue Ocean Strategy.

Reduce Capital Expenditure by avoiding building of an online platform for selling music	Create A music box with over 5000 preloaded old & retro original classics. For the nostalgic not so tech savvy generation
Eliminate The dependence on technology and internet every time one needs to hear music	Raise The product was created for the old to be purchased and gifted by the new generation.

Table 2. Four Action Framework of Blue Ocean Strategy by Saregama

The reduce and eliminate blocks help in the reduction of cost structure and the create & raise blocks work towards creating Value for Customer, thus leading to Value Innovation

The application of the Four action framework led to the Blue Ocean strategy Canvas as shown in Fig 1.2, where the blue line denotes the strategy undertaken by Saregama Carvaan, while the orange and red lines symbolise the strategies of its competitors Gaana and Saavn respectively.

Fig.1.2. BOS of Saregama Carvaan (author’s creation)

If we observe carefully in fig1.2 Saregama is playing in the market space where its competitors are not even existing thus making it easier for the company to make profit and attain its leadership.

Let’s observe the change in SWOT position of Saregama owing to application of BOS:

Strength:

- Providing the customers original old retro songs, Saregama already had a vast library of original songs so instead of providing the same facility as its competitors it created a new demand for itself.
- Striking the perfect balance between customer and consumer-Master blaster marketing strategy, Youngsters often find a dearth of option when gifting something personalised and special to their parents or grandparents. This GAP was very well identified and thus a balance was created between who use the product and who would actually buy the product as gift. Thereby sticking an emotional chord with the product making it even more special.
- Precision in targeting the product to older not so tech savvy and nostalgic consumers
- Saregama was losing its revenue because of the huge capital cost and in order to compete in red ocean with Gaana /Saavn it had to again invest in building an online platform which it avoided by pivoting its business model.
- Weakness:
- Capital expenditure on production of the Carvaan box in the look of a transistor or age-old nostalgic radio
- Distribution expenses

- Selling and Advertising Expenses
- Opportunities:
- Easy entry in the regional market.
- Tier I cities immense success made accessing the Tier II cities very easy
- The vast library of old songs and Geetmala on which Saregama owns a copyright could be put to best use
- Threats:
- Not that portable as compared to online music apps.
- Expensive compared to competitors
- Imitation in terms of looks could be easy

6.2. Strategy Analysis of Netflix:

Netflix an American entertainment company is one of the largest OTT services providing companies operating worldwide. Reed Hastings and Marc Randolph founded it in the year 1997 in Scotts Valley, California. It started off with the business plan of creating an online platform for DVD sales and also DVD rentals where the customer had to pay rent for each movie opted for. Since the time of its inception, it has continuously changed its business plan from rental per movie to monthly fees to online streaming of movies and serials in order to cater to the changing needs of the customers. This continuous change in the business plan was a Blue Ocean Strategy adopted by Netflix to remain ahead of its competitors like Blockbuster and to create a strong brand image for itself. By the year 2012 it became a worldwide online movie streaming website and also came up with ‘Netflix Originals’ showing original content in the form of movies and series through its online library. All these have led Netflix to become a strong, dynamic, successful global company. As of April 2019, it had total 154 million subscriptions (including free trials) of which 148 million are paid subscriptions.

Strengths	Weakness
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. It was the world’s first online DVD sales and rental store. Giving such services online was the first of its kind in the world. 2. It required less investment of capital as it operated online in comparison to setting up a brick-and-mortar store. 3. Huge collection of DVDs for sale and rental. It had around 925 titles which was almost the entire range of DVDs available at that time. 4. Ease of accessibility of DVDs by the customers. The DVDs were sent to the customers by mail. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The idea of using an online platform to sell and to give movies on rent was an absolutely new and untested one. 2. Brand awareness and recognition was less as compared to competitors like Blockbuster. 3. It started its business with merely 30 employees. 4. Technical issues in the form of weak internet connection.
Opportunities	Threats
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Enter larger geographical areas due conducting business online. 2. Further use of technology to expand the business idea. 3. Charging lower prices from the customers due to the low establishment costs. 4. Using the online platform for streaming varied type of content. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Competition from well-known and established companies like Blockbuster. 2. Continuous change in technology. 3. Low internet penetration in many regions.

Table 3. The SWOT Analysis of Netflix (at the time of its foundation)

Netflix had the vision to come out of the existing red ocean of completion and enter its own blue ocean by creating a new uncontested market space. It was thus able to add to its strengths by minimizing its weaknesses, making good and real use of the opportunities and removing the possible threats. From 1999 till date, it has opted for continuous product changes to make the competition irrelevant. It first distinguished itself from its competitors by starting a monthly subscription fee from the customers removing the concepts of due dates and late fees. It then started online streaming of movies and shows and also providing commercial free viewership to the customers. The digital content provided by Netflix includes a wide range of movies, television shows, videos, popular shows from foreign countries, documentaries, educational content and also its original content in the form of series and movie. The online streaming allows customers to watch anytime, anywhere and as many times as they want and they can also play, pause and resume watching as per their convenience. It also entered into partnerships with Apple TV and other smart TVs for installing built in app of Netflix to provide ease of access to the customers. It also has also developed a smart algorithm that makes suggestions to the

customers on the basis of their past watch history. It can be viewed on a number of devices like smart-phones, computers, smart TV, PlayStation etc. and it also provides the feature of parental filtering to help control the content available for children. Netflix has thus successfully implemented the four-action framework of-Eliminate, Reduce, Raise and Create of a Blue Ocean Strategy to become a leader in the digital content media.

<p style="text-align: center;">Eliminate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brick and mortar stores. • DVDs. • Storage capacity. • Late fine and due dates. • Commercials. 	<p style="text-align: center;">Reduce</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subscription fees. • Price for obtaining license. • Customer’s efforts to watch a movie.
<p style="text-align: center;">Raise</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comfort of watching. • Easy payment method. • Huge variety and volume of content to watch. • Accessibility and convenience of watching. • The number of devices which can support Netflix. 	<p style="text-align: center;">Create</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Original content in the form of movies, series, videos etc. • Region specific original content to attract the local customers. • Smart algorithm to make suggestions to the customers. • Parental filtering to control the content available for children.

Table 4. The four action framework of Netflix

The application of the Four action framework led to the Blue Ocean strategy Canvas as shown in Fig 1.3, where the blue line denotes the strategy undertaken by Netflix, while the orange line symbolises the strategy of its competitor traditional stores.

Fig: 1.3: BOS of Netflix (author’s creation)

If we observe carefully in fig1.3 Netflix is operating in the market space where its competitors are not even existing thus making it easier for the company to make profit and attain its leadership.

In the light of its successful implementation of Blue Ocean Strategy it has become imperative to do a SWOT Analysis of Netflix in the present scenario.

Strengths:

1. Netflix has become a strong, popular, successful global brand. It gives it a bargaining power while dealing with the various media houses.
2. In 2018 it had 7100 employees.
3. It has a huge and loyal customer base which is increasing with each passing day. It provides its services in 190 countries.

4. A large variety of content to watch including movies, videos, documentaries, and series, foreign shows etc.
5. It also shows original content in the form of movies, series etc. It produces and diversifies content on the basis of the region/country.
6. It can be viewed on a number of internet connected devices like television, mobile phones, computers etc.
7. Customers can binge watch the shows and also the customers do not have to face interruptions in the form of commercials.
8. Its pricing strategy is very convenient and affordable for the customers as it provides them with multiple subscription plans. Providing the first trial month for free also attracts the viewers.
9. Simple and user-friendly interface makes it easier to access.
10. It supports 22 languages including Arabic, French, Spanish, Dutch, and Japanese etc.

Weakness:

1. To operate in 190 countries, it requires a huge amount of money for its operations. This has resulted in large debt for the company.
2. It has to regularly keep on updating and adding new original content to its library to meet the increasing demand of the customers.
3. It does not have rights on the shows. Once the right expires the show will not be available anymore. It can be shown on rival platform too.
4. The subscription charges are slowly increasing.
5. Lack of environment friendly initiatives in its operations as compared to its competitor like Amazon.
6. Sometimes technical issues like slow internet connection can pose a problem to the viewers.

Opportunity:

1. Expanding their operations in the other untapped countries like China, North Korea, and Syria and also entering into partnerships with the companies in Europe like BBC to get access to the huge collection of domestic content in these regions and show it globally.
2. It can enter into partnerships with the local service providers in uncovered countries like China to provide their original content there.
3. It can start showing very old black and white movies to attract the older generation.

Threat:

1. Growing competition from Amazon, Hulu, and HBO etc.
2. Government regulations on service providers to be followed in the various countries.
3. Digital piracy leads to downloading of huge content.

7. Findings and Conclusion

By looking across time—from the value a market delivers today to the value it might deliver tomorrow—managers can actively shape their future by implementing a Blue Ocean Strategy from time to time. The study confirms the following findings:

1. Application of Blue Ocean strategy is not restricted to mere addition of a new product line or new technology to existing product. It is about creation of completely new market which has not yet being explored.
2. Saregama utilised its strength and opportunities to create value /gains for the consumers and reduced its weakness and threats to eliminate the pains of the consumers
3. The application of Blue ocean strategy lead to increase in customer base of Saregama
4. In India, vernacular and personalization are one of the most striking success factors for Carvaan. Regional variants further added to its relevance in the diversified choices and music taste of Indian markets.
5. In March 2019 the annual revenue earned by Saregama was 51.7 million dollars. The major reason behind that being the pivoted strategy of Blue Ocean.
6. Netflix is the leading global company providing digital content across 190 countries.
7. Netflix has over 148 million paid subscriptions throughout the world.
8. The net income of Netflix for the three months ended March 2019 was \$ 344,052.
9. The total assets of Netflix as on March 2019 were \$ 27,218,632
10. Netflix implemented the Blue Ocean Strategy in two stages. The first stage was the use of an online platform to sell, rent and stream movies and other digital content. When competitors began to use similar business ideas it entered into the second stage of Blue Ocean Strategy by coming up with its original digital content.

Thus, we may conclude from the above study that both the companies were able to acquire a leading position and become a successful in their respective markets because of their ability to differentiate themselves from their competitors and creating a new market space by providing the customers with an absolutely innovative product at affordable prices that changed the entertainment media industry completely. They created value

innovation for their customers leading to the increased level of customer satisfaction and increasing their customer base.

However, certain recommendations can be made for both the companies keeping in mind the probable competition that they may have to face in the future:

- Saregama Carvaan device could be made a little more portable and convenient to carry.
- The battery life of Saregama Carvaan is limited to five hours only which makes it a little vulnerable for prolonged use.
- Browsing for content and finding specific tracks in Carvaan is a tedious and flawed approach which could be worked on to make it more customer friendly
- The speaker quality is average which could be worked on for a better consumer experience.
- Saregama Carvaan should target smaller towns and rural areas along with Tier I & II cities.
- Netflix should increase the options of subscription fees.
- Netflix should strengthen its security to avoid digital piracy of its content.
- Netflix should enter into agreements with various internet service providers to provide ratings of movies to the customers.
- Netflix should try to enter into uncovered countries to acquire the huge customer base there.
- Netflix should try to improve its feature of making recommendations to the viewers.

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